

MODE FUNCTIONALITY

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Annotation: In this article, classification of lad functionality, its main factors and components, different views of researchers are highlighted. Besides it is focused to the fact that in new modal concepts, both harmonic and melodic systems, one had to use long-established terminology, burdened by the burden of previous ideas and associations, not to mention more significant reasons.

Keywords: mode, modal theory, monody, pitch, chord-tonal interaction, acoustic considerations, integral structures.

The key meaning of the concept of “mode functionality” is determined, first of all, by the fact that mode is not conceivable outside the qualitative relationships of tones, a “logically differentiated” (Y. Tyulin) system of relations. The concept of a function plays a fundamental role in modal theories because no other modal system, except for a functionally designed one, exists. Otherwise, as you know, it turns out to be a fixed series of sounds - a scale that is only the acoustic material of musical speech. And this means that only the revelation of the functional structure of the mode will actually be its disclosure.

Without touching now on many issues of the pitch organization in monody, let us turn to those of its features that determine both its originality and the specifics of the methods for studying modes of the monodic type.

The most developed and complete theory of pitch functionality today has developed, as is known, in the doctrine of harmony, the foundations of which were laid by J.F. Rameau, and the system development and classically completed form received from G. Riemann, F. Fetis, Y. Tyulin.

1) actually chord-tonal interactions are endowed, first of all, with chord formations;

2) as elements of a polyphonic musical fabric, it is the chords that form the basis of the tonal structure and predetermine the principle of its dynamic centralization. Moreover, based on acoustic considerations, fourth-quint ratios are preferred.

However, along with the system of harmonic relations, the so-called melodic functionality was singled out, a specific sound form of implementation and, in essence, the only interval expression of which is the second ratio of tones, and sometimes chords. At the same time, these pitch ratios and the melodic form of functionality associated with it are considered to be derivatives of harmonic patterns and are directly dependent and logically subordinate to the latter.

In other words, a special place in the classical theory is occupied by statements of specific interval forms of the tonal system; quarto-fifth and second ratios have become, in fact, the decisive criterion for differentiating the two types of functionality. On these prerequisites, a number of very stable positions were formed, among which were the following: in the pitch relationships between the elements of the musical fabric (sounds, interval formations, etc.), the modal dynamic forces reach a special concentration precisely in chord-harmonic complexes; chords have an effectiveformative power and the ability to influence intonation processes (including melodic ones); and therefore the tonal principle of modal organization is possible when and where chords become an element of the musical fabric as special integral structures. Naturally, on this basis, outside systems of harmonic type, the real functionality [34, p. 16-18], i.e. the dynamic relationships that form the tonal system were often excluded a priori.

However, these ideas were very soon called into question, which was facilitated by the increased interest in pre-classical European music and, even more so, in numerous non-European and generally non-harmonic musical cultures. Numerous contradictions were also discovered between established views and the new that the

composers' work brought with it in the 20th century. It became more and more obvious that the traditional functional theory is not universal, that it is limited by the historical and stylistic framework and is “motivated” by specifically defined types of composition of the musical fabric.

And as a result, more and more broad interpretations of the concept of modal (tonal) function began to appear, its more general definitions arose, incorporating any manifestations of pitch coordination of tones. So already in the 80s. some authors began to regard as functional the whole set of relationships between the elements of the musical fabric, regardless of what these elements are - chords, individual tones or interval structures and in what pitch-interval relationships they are (in the educational literature it was reflected

N. Gulyanitskaya. Obviously, this was a completely justified and even forced departure from the orientation towards specific, strictly defined forms of expression of functional relations. The need for it was felt by many researchers, although it was solved in different ways. In the end, the outlined overcoming of traditional ideas reached a critical point, after which attempts were made to radically rethink the very concept of harmony functionality (primarily in the works of Y. Kholopov, S. Galitskaya, A. Yusfin, A. Milka and others).

Although, the fact that in new modal concepts, both harmonic and melodic systems, one had to use long-established terminology, burdened by the burden of previous ideas and associations, not to mention more significant reasons, could not but affect. First of all, that the main provisions of the traditional theory were extrapolated to systems far removed from the principles of classical tonality. In this case, it is not important whether this extrapolation has a “positive” or “negative” character. In the first case, it was expressed in the desire to see isomorphic principles of modal organization in any, even in the most diverse musical systems, and this was noticeable at the beginning of the study of monodic cultures, when faith in the universality of classical theory had not yet been shaken. The second trend has prevailed at the present

time, when the inconsistency of a direct transfer of classical postulates and conclusions to the field of monody has become obvious.

Indeed, it has already become quite common to oppose harmonic and monodic systems literally according to all the formal-structural and qualitative parameters known to the theory. And often in the form of axioms that do not require complex, and sometimes scrupulous proofs. So it became almost mandatory:

- to oppose the dynamism of the functional relations of harmonic systems - "demagnetization" and "softness" of the gravity of tones in monody;

- the unambiguous nature of the harmonic tonic - the opposite qualities of monody, i.e. "the predominance of differentiation of precisely stability", "qualitative individualization of stable functions";

- "autonomy of the harmonic system", capable of controlling the intonation process and possessing formative power - "the effectiveness of monodic modes", the functionality of tones, in which it is completely dependent on syntactic, rhythmo-intonation and other conditions;

- the dynamic aspiration of the modal functions of the first one - "the predominance of inhibitory tendencies in monody"¹;

- the centralizing role of the main element of the harmonic system - in general, the absence of such in monody (total alternation, decentralization);

- the constructive meaning of the height-spatial coordinate in the European polyphony - not the typicality of "any, even the implied vertical dimensions"² "one-line monody", one-line pitch functionality.

- "structuring" tones into regularly formed chords-complexes, which "are only" modally significant in European polyphony - the principle of monody, where "each tone has its own unique function of another tone"³;

¹ Galitskaya S. Theoretical questions of monody. – T., 1981. 56-p.

² Bershatkaya T. Lectures on harmony. - L., 1987. 14-p.

³ Alekseev E. Problems of mode formation. - M., 1976.

- the identity of the tones of the octave ratio - the fundamental absence of such, and so on.

The functional method is certainly not a panacea for all problems, but the specificity of monodic intonation makes it indispensable. In the analysis of monody, one cannot hide behind the description of complex sound constructions and structural refinements, since its “form” is simple. Unless, of course, you stoop to primitive formal statements. But she fully compensates for this with the depth of intonational meaning, the play and plasticity of melos arranged in a modally organized manner. In the modal analysis of monody, all the more, one cannot do without, in the words of B.Asafiev, “an auditory sensation of qualitative tones” and “intonational representation of intervals”, without a musical analysis of “the intensity of sound distances”.

That is, without listening to the really modal meaning of sound structures. And do not rush to conclusions, grasping at the familiar outlines of sound forms, as something originally “by nature” modally pre-established. There are no and cannot be functionally predetermined structures (steps, intervals, sound ratios, etc.) endowed with modal qualities supposedly according to the property of the sound material.

And finally, this approach is based on the hypothesis that the principle of dynamic centralization of the mode, with the corresponding functional system as a type, is universal, although the “principle of centralizing unity” itself is one of the possible forms of mode organization, whether it concerns harmonic and monodic music. Moreover, the very generality of a principle does not at all mean that it will be expressed everywhere in the same way.

Depending on the musical language and musical thinking of a given culture, on many other factors (instrumental and vocal types of creativity, the established compositional norms of forms, and many others), this principle acquires its own individual certainty, a fairly pronounced uniqueness. The same laws of pitch organization as some kind of logical universals and "abstracted system of musical thinking", even if we assume such, can generally have a wide range of sound forms of

their embodiment. Let us only emphasize that it is precisely these “external forms of expression” of the principle of centralizing unity that may be the “most essential” thing that should be studied, since they do not exist for the principles, but, on the contrary, it itself is only one of the ways to implement modally organized musical intonation.

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